

THE IMPACT OF THE PRODUCT STRATEGY ON THE MARKET SHARE. THE CASE OF BULGARIAN WINERIES

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Abstract

Product strategy is one of the main factors which determining market share. Two variables are important in planning of the product strategy of winery – one is the level of specialization (diversification) of production and second is the scale of production. This raises the question of what is an appropriate product strategy to be followed and how it will affect the market power and efficiency of management of wineries. The purpose of this study is to analyze and assess the impact of product strategy on market share and to measure how market share influence the efficiency of the wineries in Bulgaria. First stage of methodological approach is to identify is there relevance between applied product strategy and achieved market share of winery. The second stage is to be evaluated the relevance between achieved market share and level of efficiency of management of wineries. The statistical evidence proof that product strategy can influence on market share and efficiency of management.

Key words: product strategy, market share, return on sales, return on equity, return on assets

Abstrakt

Die Produktstrategie ist einer der Hauptfaktoren, die den Marktanteil bestimmen. Zwei Variablen sind bei der Planung der Produktstrategie der Weinkellerei wichtig - zum einen der Grad der Spezialisierung (Diversifizierung) der Produktion und zum anderen der Umfang der Produktion. Dies wirft die Frage auf, welche Produktstrategie zu verfolgen ist und wie sie sich auf die Marktmacht und die Effizienz des Managements der Weinkellereien auswirkt. Der Zweck dieser Studie ist es, die Auswirkungen der Produktstrategie auf den Marktanteil zu analysieren und zu bewerten und zu messen, wie der Marktanteil die Effizienz der Weinkellereien in Bulgarien beeinflusst. Die erste Stufe des methodischen Ansatzes besteht darin, die Relevanz zwischen der angewandten Produktstrategie und dem erreichten Marktanteil der Weinkellereien zu ermitteln. In der zweiten Phase soll die Relevanz zwischen dem erreichten Marktanteil und dem Grad der Effizienz des Managements der Weinkellereien bewertet werden. Die statistischen Beweise beweisen, dass die Produktstrategie den Marktanteil und die Effizienz des Managements beeinflussen kann.

Schlüsselwörter: Produktstrategie, Marktanteil, Umsatzrendite, Eigenkapitalrendite, Kapitalrendite

Résumé

La stratégie de produit est l'un des principaux facteurs qui déterminent la part de marché. Deux variables sont importantes dans la planification de la stratégie de produit d'une entreprise vinicole - l'une est le niveau de spécialisation (diversification) de la production et l'autre est l'échelle de production. Cela soulève la question de savoir quelle est la stratégie de produit appropriée à suivre et comment elle

affectera le pouvoir de marché et l'efficacité de la gestion des établissements vinicoles. L'objectif de cette étude est d'analyser et d'évaluer l'impact de la stratégie de produit sur la part de marché et de mesurer comment la part de marché influence l'efficacité des caves en Bulgarie. La première étape de l'approche méthodologique consiste à identifier la pertinence de la stratégie de produit appliquée et la part de marché atteinte par les caves. La deuxième étape consiste à évaluer la pertinence entre la part de marché obtenue et le niveau d'efficacité de la gestion des établissements vinicoles. Les données statistiques prouvent que la stratégie de produit peut avoir une influence sur la part de marché et l'efficacité de la gestion.

Mots clés: stratégie de produit, part de marché, rendement des ventes, rendement des capitaux propres, rendement des actifs

Introduction

In terms of market surplus and strong price competition in the global wine market, the main tool for maintaining market power of enterprise is the objectively developed and pursued integrated product strategy. Wine enterprises in Bulgaria have serious gaps in strategic marketing activities. Results of the recent study (Radev, 2012) show the presence of significant gaps in basic marketing activities such as the establishment of a functioning information system, market segmentation, developing profile of target market, quantitative setting marketing objectives, build a system for monitoring the implementation of the marketing strategy. In most of the surveyed wine enterprises these activities are ignored (in whole or in part), which calls into question the quality and those that are running. The final process of developing and following a product strategy is the result of successive steps and cannot be done if the previous missing. In the domestic market, wineries are seeking to implement flexible pricing as a leading factor for their product strategy. This is determined by the fact that consumers have low income and in the choice of buying leading factor is the relation "price-quality". On the other hand, there are some major problems on the value proposition chain like small size of the vine farms which are main producers of raw materials; deteriorating age structure of the vineyards; low share of typical Bulgarian grape varieties in the variety structure; large share of the informal sector and low integration of industries (Dimitrova, 2010), (Borisov, Marinov 2013). In these conditions, the ability of product strategy to ensure market share which brings greater return on investments is a really real indicator of effective management thinking. Managers must increase the return on investment to meet the requirements of investors, but on the other hand it is necessary to take into account market requirements and restriction of business condition in the development of adaptive product strategy. Product strategy is one of the main factors which determining market share (Avila, 1997), (Gorynia, 2004). One strategy to achieve greater market share is maintaining a diversified line of products, which complicates the management of the enterprise as a whole (Liao, 2005), (Ivanov, 2013). Another strategy is to achieve a high degree of specialization and standardization of large-scale production, which allow achieving price leadership (Armstrong, 1996). Several studies show that there is direct relationship between manufacturing capacity and market share of the enterprise (Galbraith, 1990; Ling, 2000; Lockshin, 2000). In conditions of large production capacity enterprise has the potential to gain greater market share, benefiting from all the advantages of large scale production. (Tirole, 1988), (Bloodgood and

Katz, 2004). Very common strategy used by wineries is the production of a limited range of products featuring high quality and respectively imposing its higher price segments (Radev, 2009). The aim of this strategy is to achieve differentiation of the offered product. Following each of these product strategies put different restrictions on the development and maintenance of market share of the winery. At higher specialization of the product range, the enterprise has a higher inertia of changes in market conditions. On the other hand maintaining a wide variety of products available, which ensures more sales and thus achieve greater market share complicates the overall management of the enterprise. This raises the question of what is an appropriate product strategy to be followed and how it will affect the market power and efficiency of management of wineries. The purpose of the current study is to analyze and measure the impact of product strategy on market share and how market share influence the efficiency of the wineries in Bulgaria.

Based on the definition of that "the product is a set of features offered by the seller to the buyer" (Trendafilov, 2000) the development of the company's product strategy applies to making strategic decisions on product characteristics. Product characteristics can be divided into two groups - real and ideal. Real characteristics are tangible and not depend on the subjective opinion of the user. These features are size, shape, weight, technical values, nutritional value, composition, packaging, shelf life, color, taste, smell. Ideal product features are intangible and their judgment depends on the subjective opinion of the user. This includes the brand, quality, and image, type of manufacturing, utility, guarantees, and aesthetics. The determination of these characteristics is an essential part of the development of product policy, but before proceeding to them, the management should determine what product range will be provided into the market. According to Kotler, 2005 the product strategy represents a "whole group of goods and items that a seller offers for sale." Managers should consider very carefully, what will be the width, depth and harmony in the product strategy. Width represents the number of product lines, the depth is the number of sets within a product line and harmony refers to the degree that combines (complement) the different product lines. Looking for opportunities to expand their business, companies can add new product lines and / or increase assortments included in a product line. It is also possible and reverses the process of optimizing existing product range in which certain sets or product lines are removed from production. Two variables are important in planning of the product strategy of winery – one is the level of specialization (width of product range) and second is the scale of production (depth of product range) (Martinet, 2010). In figure 1 is given matrix build into the mentioned criteria – scale of production and level of specialization.

Figure 1. Types of strategies of wineries. Source: Adapted according to the criteria of Martinet, 2010.

Depth of product range		Width of product range	
		Small/ under 50 000 bottles per line	Large/ more than 500 000 bottles per line
	Specialized / only one product line	(1) Small-scale specialized strategy	(2) Large-scale specialized strategy
	Diversified / two and more product lines	(3) Small-scale diversified strategy	(4) Large-scale diversified strategy

The matrix shows four different types of product strategies, which wineries applied in their market policy.

The proper combination of these two factors can lead to adaptive product strategy. In table 1 is given the types and aims of each product strategy which are included in current study. According to the interviewed managers of wineries small scaled product line has capacity up to 50 000 bottles per year and large scale line has capacity to produce up to 500 000 bottles per year. Highly specialized wineries are those who produce only one product line and diversified is those who produce more than two product lines.

Table 1. Comparative analysis of product strategies of wineries in Bulgaria. Source: own survey, 2019

Type of product strategy	Characteristic	Aim	Indicators for efficiency of management of winery
Small scale specialization	Winery is specialized in production of one product line in limited capacity /under 50 000 bottles/	Higher price Quality product Exclusiveness	Return on sales Return on equity Return on assets
Large scale specialization	Winery is specialized in production of one product line in large capacity /more than 500 000 bottles/	Standardization Economies of scale Price leadership which benefits more sales	Return on sales Return on equity Return on assets
Small scale diversification	Winery is specialized in production of two and more product lines in limited capacity /more than 50 000 bottles for each one/	Higher price Quality product Exclusiveness More choice for consumers	Return on sales Return on equity Return on assets
Large scale diversification	Winery is specialized in production of two and more product lines in large capacity /more than 500 000 bottles for each one/	More coverage of consumer preferences which benefits more sales Greater market share	Return on sales Return on equity Return on assets

First stage of methodological approach is to identify is there relevance between applied product strategy and achieved market share of winery (see figure 2). By applying χ^2 - analysis is assessed the mentioned relevance.

The second stage is to be evaluated the relevance between achieved market share and level of efficiency of management of wineries. According to Rajaram (2010) indicators for efficiency of management of enterprise are return on sales, return on equity and return on assets. By applying statistical approach, called regression is testing what is the impact of market share on efficiency of management of winery. In this regression model, market share is situated as a driver and return of sales, equity and assets are functional factors (which characterized the efficiency of management).

Figure 2. Methodological approach of study. Source: Own, 2019.

All data is collected by using structural interviews with managers and financial reports of wineries. In the study, take part 55 wineries from each wine region of Bulgaria in period 2010-2013. All collected data is process with MS Excel. The statistical analysis is provided by using the software - ANOVA and SPSS.

SAMPLE

Table 2 shows the structure of the sample. According to the results of the survey among the managers of the observed wineries, dominate those with small-scale production of only one product line in 50 000 bottles per year (40% of total). 30% of studied wineries have two product lines with capacity up to 100 000 bottles per line. The rest of wineries have 3 and more product lines with range up and more than 300 000 bottles.

Table 2. Structure of the sample. Own survey, 2019.

Number of wineries	Number of product lines	Scale of product line
22 (40% of total)	up to 1	under 50 000 bottles per line
17 (30% of total)	up to 2	up to 100 000 bottles per line
9 (16% of total)	up to 3	up to 300 000 bottles per line
7 (13% of total)	more than 3	more than 300 000 bottles per line

Source: Own survey, 2010-2013.

The summarized data from the conducted survey shows that 40% of observed wineries applied small scale specialization of production, followed by 33% of those which apply large scale specialized strategy. It is obvious that wineries prefer to be more specialized (to produce one or two product lines) in their product strategy than following diversity.

Figure 3. Structure of the applied strategies. Source: Own survey, 2019

Results

Frequency distributions obtained by applying χ^2 - analysis reveal the impact of product strategy, which is not random relating to the market share. The results of χ^2 - analysis are shown in Table 3. The obtained results are at significance level $\alpha = 0,05$. The strength of the established statistical relevance is measured by the coefficient of Kramer. According to the Kramer's coefficient there is very strong relevance between large-scale diversification strategy and market share (see table 3). The statistical analysis shows that market share is determined by the strategy of diversification of product range in large-scale production. Wineries who can obtain a numerous large-scale product lines in product folio achieve faster and greater market share. Small-scaled specialized production also can lead the winery to the greater market share (Kramer's coefficient is 0,6541). There is no relation between small-scaled diversified strategy and market share. It can be summarized that applying strategies - (1) and (4) can lead to greater market share.

Table 3. Statistical verification of relation between product strategy and market share. Source: Own survey, 2019.

Type of strategy	Results of χ^2 - analysis	
	Is there a relevance?	Kramer's coefficient
(1) Small scale specialization	there is	0,6541
(2) Large scale specialization	there is	0,5465
(3) Small scale diversification	there is not	0,3216
(4) Large scale diversification	there is	0,8855

In table 4 are shown the results of regression analysis between market share and indicators, which measure the efficiency of management of studied wineries. All studied relevancies are positive which means that higher market share cause higher returns on sales, on equity and on assets of the winery. Market share has very strong impact on return of sales (see table 4, Multiple R has value 0,9524) and strong impact on returns on equity and on assets.

Table 4. Results of regression between market share and achieved efficiency. Source: Own calculation based on Methodological approach of the study

Relevance	Driver	Result	Type of relevance	Multiple R	Degree of relevance
Relevance between market share and return on sales	Market share	Return of sales	Positive	0,9524	Very strong
Relevance between market share and return on equity	Market share	Return of equity	Positive	0,8593	Strong
Relevance between market share and return on assets	Market share	Return of assets	Positive	0,7825	Strong

In table 5 is given the comparative analysis of the impacts of product strategies on market share and returns of studied wineries. Wineries which apply diversification on large scale as product strategy have bigger market share – 11,2%. Following strategy (3) lead to the smallest market share – 0,2%. Higher returns on sales (14,7% and 11,3%) have wineries which apply strategies – (4) and (2). Also the same strategies lead and to higher returns on equity and on assets.

Table 4. Efficiency of the different product strategies. Source: Own survey, 2019.

Type of strategy	Market share %	Return on sales %	Return on equity %	Return on assets %
(1) Small scale specialization	0,8*	6,7	1,02	0,01
(2) Large scale specialization	1,8	11,3	2,9	0,6
(3) Small scale diversification	0,2	-0,4	-3,5	-0,5
(4) Large scale diversification	11,2	14,7	2,1	0,8

* average market shares per enterprise

By using matrix approach into interpretation of the results from regression statistical analysis can be further analyzed the impact of product strategy on market power and efficiency of the management. On table 6 is shown the impact of each product strategy on change of market share and change of return on sales (between mentioned two factors there is very strong relevance according to the regression analysis, see table 4). Wineries, which apply large-scale diversification, achieved larger market share and gain higher return of sales. This product strategy benefits market power and valorization of market power. Large-scale specialization of winery drives to increase in return of sales and decrease in market share. In other words, this strategy gives opportunity to enhance the returns on sales achieved by smaller market share. Wineries, which follow small-scale specialization strategy achieve lower rate of returns on sales but they obtained larger market share. This means that they enhance their market power but could not benefit it with higher returns. Following small-scale diversification as a product strategy leads to decrease in market share and return on sales.

Table 6. Matrix of market share and return on sales. Source: Own calculation, 2019

	Increase of market share	Decrease of market share
Increase of return on sales	(3) large scale diversification	(2) large scale specialization
Decrease of return on sales	(1) small scale specialization	(4) small scale diversification

Conclusions

The results from statistical analysis proof that product strategy has influence on market share and efficiency of management in sector. Strategy of large-scaled product lines has better ability to gain market power and returns on sales. The wineries who applied them can manage very well the economies of scale. Obtaining diversification of products also give another competitive advantage of wineries. They can cover more consumer preferences by providing them a wide selection of different wines. The strategy of

specialization leads to standardization of wine producing. Those factor benefits price leadership, which is suitable condition for gaining market share.

It can be summarized that the scale of production is the most important factor for achieving market share in sector. Applying strategy of diversification leads to greater return on sales by achieving higher market share. On the other hand, strategy of specialization can provide almost the same returns on sales by achieving less market share.

The results of empirical research show that large-scale diversification of product folio is the best product strategy according to the increase of market share and return on sales. Winery, which offers different types of wines and wine products in large-scale cover more costumer's requirements and fast gain market share also, benefits economy from large scale of production.

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